

FWO & Open Science

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Vlaanderen
is wetenschap

FWO en Open Science

► Basic distinction

- FWO as a funder of fundamental and strategic basic research
 - × With its own Open Science Policy
 - × In dialogue with international community
 - [Open Science - Science Europe](#)

- Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB) – Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN)
 - × Coordination hosted by FWO
 - × FWO member among the other Flemish institutions (VLAIO, universities, research institutes, strategic research centres, university colleges)
 - × Development of common policy for Flanders

FRDN

Open Science: why?

- ▶ Better science through sharing and cooperation
 - Creating Synergies
 - Accelerating science
 - More insights on the basis of accessible and/or integrated data
 - Avoiding duplication
- ▶ More dissemination of results to a broader audience, diverse stakeholders, ...
- ▶ Research Integrity and accountability

Open Science: many dimensions

- ▶ **Open Access to Publications** – different routes
- ▶ **Open & FAIR Data** – from preservation/storage (FAIR) to sharing
- ▶ Open Review
- ▶ Open Source Software
- ▶ Open Infrastructuur
- ▶ Citizen Science

- ▶ **Always respecting specificities**
 - Domain, discipline
 - Research question, methodology
 - Type of research

- ▶ A **way** to go, not merely a **goal** in itself

General Regulations, art. 4: Open Access

§ 4. These researchers must also include the **reference information for the publications in the systems of the relevant host institution** and, via the relevant institution, **in the FRIS research portal** (if the host institution in question has undertaken to provide information to FRIS). When mentioned in the repository, a **label** must be clearly assigned indicating that this publication was created with funding from (among others) the FWO. A **link** must be created in the system and in the FRIS research portal between the FWO funding programme, the FWO file number of the project/fellowship/FWO funding and the relevant publication that at least in part was realised with the help of FWO funding. From 2024, **only publications submitted to the FRIS research portal** through the systems of the relevant host institution (if the relevant host institution has undertaken to provide information to FRIS) **will be taken into account when evaluating scientific reports.**

General Regulations, art. 2: Open Access

▶ Why?

→ Publicly funded research should also be publicly available.

▶ What?

→ Publications resulting (partly) from FWO funding → **Focus: peer reviewed journal articles**

→ Also applies to already ongoing fellowships/projects/grants

▶ How?

→ Published in an OA database (“green” OA) → Minimum requirement

→ Full (“gold”) or partly (“hybrid”) OA journals or Diamond OA → Bench fee/Consumables budget

▶ When?

→ Green OA selected? Maximum embargo period of 12 months

→ Right implemented in Belgian federal law (Art. XI.196, §2/1 of the Economic Law Code)

▶ Further reading?

→ <https://www.fwo.be/en/the-fwo/research-policy/open-access/>

→ FWO General Regulations, article 2, paragraph 2: <https://www.fwo.be/en/general-regulations/>

→ Scientific integrity: <https://thinkchecksubmit.org/>

General Regulations, art. 4: Research Data

§ 5. Information about **datasets** linked to **FWO-funded projects and fellowships and/or to publications resulting from FWO** funding must be **included in the systems of the relevant host institution** and, via the relevant host institution, **in the FRIS research portal** (if the host institution has undertaken to provide information to FRIS).

→ Also eligible cost bench fee/consumables

Further reading:

<https://fwo.be/en/about-fwo/research-policy/research-results/>

<https://www.ewi-vlaanderen.be/onze-opdracht/innoverende-samenleving/fris-flanders-research-information-space>

Data Management Plan (DMP)

- ▶ In application forms already 6 questions
- ▶ Not decisive for selection
- ▶ A full DMP is required for funded projects/fellowships within 6 months after official start
- ▶ Part of final report & evaluation project/fellowship+
- ▶ Further reading: <https://www.fwo.be/en/about-fwo/research-policy/data-management-plan-dmp/>

Data Management Plan (DMP)

► Questions in application

1. Describe the **datatypes** (surveys, sequences, manuscripts, objects ...) the research will collect and/or generate and /or (re)use. (use up to 700 characters)
2. Specify in which way the following **provisions** are in place in order to preserve the data during and **at least 5 years after the end** of the research? Motivate your answer. (use up to 700 characters)
 - a. Designation **of responsible person** (If already designated, please fill in his/her name.)
 - b. **Storage capacity/repository**
 - during the research
 - after the research
3. What's the reason why you wish to **deviate** from the principle of preservation of data and of the minimum preservation term of 5 years? (max. 700 characters)

Data Management Plan (DMP)

4. Are there issues concerning research data indicated in the **ethics** questionnaire of this application form? Which specific security measures do those data require? (use up to 700 characters)
5. Which **other issues** related to the data management are relevant to mention? (use up to 700 characters)
6. For whom might your data be **useful outside of the research project**, e.g. researchers or other stakeholders? How will you share this data?

Open Science in evaluation: ex ante (projects a.o.)

‘SECOND AXIS’

▶ Broadening our view on diverse research(ers) profiles

- Narrative, more than only ‘classic’ output and extensive definition of ‘impact’
- CV with a broad set of activities
- Publication list: A.1.1. & A.1.2. > A1: peer review art.
 - × For entire list: only publications from last 10 years
- 5 main publications and/or achievements

▶ Integrated in application, evaluation and communication

Open Science in evaluation: ex ante (projects a.o.)

▶ Extra highlighting Open Science achievements and impact

→ CV

- × 'Publications': question on **PID**
- × Examples of 'achievements' (**datasets, research software**), question on **metadata**
- × Option to mention **datasets, grey literature and research software** as examples of 'other scientific output & impact'

→ Application form

- × 'Requested funding': **consumables with regard to OS explicitly mentioned**
- × 'Research methodology & work plan'
 - *Discuss which measures will be taken to make the research **transparent and reproducible**.*
 - *Describe how you will **disseminate your research** (as different from the kind of dissemination mentioned under 'Science Communication').*
- × DMP: extra question in DMP section
 - **For whom might your data be useful outside of the research project, e.g. researchers or other stakeholders? How will you share this data?**

Open Science in evaluation: ex ante (projects a.o.)

- ▶ **Extra highlighting Open Science achievements and impact**

- Scoring grid

- × Measures taken to make the research more transparent or reproducible can increase score for project, criterium 2B.

Scoring grid Project

0R	1R	2R	3R	4R	5R	6R	7R
UnacceptableR	WeakR	Fair/reasonableR		Good/very-goodR		Excellent/outstandingR	
2.a. Scientific quality, relevance of the research project & originalityR							
The proposal contains structural flaws and/or does not offer scientific added value to the international state of the art and to already ongoing research. ¶ and/or ¶ The project does not contain real scientific risks or challenges. ¶	The added value of the proposal w.r.t. the international state of the art and to ongoing research is limited. The project is rather a catching-up effort. ¶ and/or ¶ Rather limited level of scientific risks and pronounced challenges ¶	The added value of the proposal relative to the international state of the art and to ongoing research is still reasonable but less pronounced or less well elaborated. ¶ and/or ¶ Not all parts of the proposal fit well with the requirements of high-risk, challenging and inventive fundamental research. ¶		The scientific goals of the proposal offer a substantial added value relative to the international state of the art and to ongoing research activities. The project builds upon the international state of the art in a sound manner. ¶ and ¶ The proposal as a whole fits well with the requirements of high-risk, challenging and inventive fundamental research. ¶		The project is highly original and very unique. It distinguishes itself in an outstanding manner from ongoing research and has large impact potential ('groundbreaking' research). The proposal demonstrates a very high level of scientific risks and shows clear inventive and challenging ideas, novel concepts and strategies. ¶	
2.b. Quality of the research approach and feasibility of the projectR							
Evident discrepancy/mismatch between research goals and research approach. ¶ and/or ¶ The realization of the scientific goals is not feasible with the proposed research approach. ¶	The research approach shows serious flaws or shortcomings. The research approach must be improved substantially. ¶ and/or ¶ The match between research goals and approach needs to be adjusted considerably. ¶ and (if applicable). ¶ The work distribution is not well-balanced taking into account the expertise of the partners. The roles of each partner are not well-defined. ¶	The research approach is reasonable but contains some gaps or shortcomings and/or leaves room for improvement. ¶ and/or ¶ The balance between scientific challenge and feasibility of the scientific project objectives is reasonable. ¶ and/or ¶ Some gaps or shortcomings in project planning and management. Resources may need to be reviewed. ¶ and (if applicable). ¶ The balance in work distribution is reasonably in line with the expertise. Reasonably well-defined roles of each partner. ¶		The proposed methodology is well-elaborated, relevant and suitable to reach the targeted scientific objectives. No significant gaps or shortcomings. ¶ and ¶ The project implementation is realistic and feasible within the four-year time frame. Timescales and resources are properly justified. ¶ and (if applicable). ¶ Good balance in work distribution taking into account the expertise of each partner. Well-defined role of each partner. ¶ and (if applicable) required for very good: ¶ appropriate measures were taken to make the research transparent and reproducible. ¶		Requirements "very good", and thorough identification of the research risks, with alternative research strategies and "fall-back" research options, ¶ and (if applicable). ¶ The research plan is focused on high level of integration, cross-fertilization and synergy between the partners. The role of each partner is clearly defined. ¶	

OS & evaluation of scientific reports

▶ Open Access

- All peer-reviewed journal articles (A1) required to be 'Open' or 'under embargo'. If any are 'closed' → **insufficient**
- Information about A1-publications automatically retrieved from FRIS
- Checked during evaluation of interim and ex post reports

▶ DMP

- A complete DMP (using the Flemish DMP template) attached to the ex post report. If this is missing → **insufficient**

▶ When receiving a negative evaluation

- After first communication: 30 calendar days to submit DMP and/or make A1-publications 'Open' or 'under embargo' → **Reassessment**
- If not remediated → **no new applications accepted for 1 year after final announcement**

Open Science and Social Sciences

- ▶ Research data management in practice: variations between disciplines and kinds of research
 - DMP already reflects that
 - But DMP itself required for all projects/fellowships
 - Consult your data steward

Open Science and Social Sciences

- ▶ FWO does not distinguish between qualitative and quantitative research for its OS policy
- ▶ Research often a combination of qualitative and quantitative approach and results
- ▶ Privacy issues can be relevant for both types

Open Science and Social Sciences

- ▶ Documentation for qualitative research results often more detailed and contextualised
- ▶ You can anonymise and pseudonymise for sharing data with personal information
 - Can be harder for qualitative data without losing valuable information
 - check with your data steward